
Extraction of Iron (III) by Tri-phenyl Arsine Oxide

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Abstract

Solvent extraction of Iron (III) from hydrochloric, Sulphuric and nitric acid solutions with Tri-phenyl arsine Oxide (TPAsO) in benzene has been studied. The extractions from hydrochloric and sulphuric acid solutions are nearly quantitative and are partial from nitric acid solutions. The optimum conditions for extraction were established from the study of the effect of several variables like concentration of the extractant, metal ion, acidity, foreign ions etc. Based on the results obtained, the probable extracted species are also identified. The method has been applied for the determination of iron in food as well as pharmaceutical samples.

Keywords: Extraction -iron (III) - Tri-Phenyl Arsine Oxide (TPAsO) – pharmaceutical samples.

1. INTRODUCTION

Solvent extraction of iron (III) has been studied with amines [1], phosphate [2, 3] and phosphine oxides [4-7]. All these studies concern with extraction of iron from one acid system. Further, no reports are available on the extraction of iron (III) from arsine oxides. Therefore, in the present communication a detailed study has been carried out on the extraction of iron (III) by Tri-phenyl arsine Oxide (TPAsO) from hydrochloric, sulphuric and nitric acid solutions and the results obtained are presented here.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A stock solution of 0.25 M TPAsO (Buchs SG, Switzerland) in benzene was prepared and diluted appropriately to get the required concentration. Ferric ammonium sulphate (E.Merck) was used for preparing iron(III) stock solution (0.5M) and was standardized using standard potassium dichromate solution volumetrically[8]. All other chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. Double distilled water was used throughout the course of investigations.

2.1 Iron (iii) extraction:

Iron (III) distribution studies were made using appropriate concentrations of the iron salt and mineral acid by equilibrating with an equal volume (10ml) of TPAsO in benzene (0.025M) pre-equilibrated with 0.1M mineral acid. The solution was shaken for 5 minutes. The two phases were allowed to settle and separate. Iron(III) from the organic phase was stripped with 10ml of 0.1M H₂SO₄. The concentration of Iron (III) in both the phases was determined by AAS method.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

The variation of distribution ratio as a function of aqueous phase concentration of the acid (HCl, H₂SO₄ and HNO₃) is presented in Table-1. From hydrochloric and sulphuric acid solutions the distribution ratio (K_d) increased sharply with increasing concentration of the acid up to 8.0 M & 9.0M acidity respectively beyond which decrease in extraction is noticed. In nitric acid media, the distribution ratio found to be decreased above 4.0M acidity.

3.1 Composition of the extracted species:

The extraction isotherm method [9] and distribution ratio method [10] were employed to determine the composition of the extracted species. In the extraction isotherm method the limiting ratio of the metal to TPAsO was found unity with all the acid systems. The log-log plots of K_d Vs. TPAsO from various acid solutions gave straight lines. The slope analysis of the distribution data in sulphuric acid solutions indicates that the solvation number is two where as in other acid solutions the log-log plots gave straight lines of unit slope.

3.2 Absorption spectra:

The individual Iron (III) extracted species with TPAsO was studied in U.V. region [11,12]. The absorption spectra from sulphuric acid media exhibits absorption band at 295 and 355 nm. These two are the absorption characteristics of Fe(OH) and hydroxyl – group bridging species Fe(OH)₂ Fe respectively, and the appearance of new peak at 305 nm corresponds to the complexes FeSO₄⁺ and Fe(SO₄)⁻².

The observed iron: TPAsO molar ratio of unity and two from different acid solutions (by distribution ratio method) could be explained as arising from the extraction of iron (III) by the following ion-exchange mechanism.

From sulphuric acid solutions:

From Other acid solutions:**3.3 Effect of stripping agents:**

After extraction, iron (III) was stripped with 20ml reagents of various concentrations (0.1 – 2.0 M) of ACOH, H₂SO₄ and NaOH solutions.. It was observed that 1.0 M HNO₃ alone is a good stripping agent. However in no case the acid strips out all the iron (III) in a single extraction 99.7% iron (III) could be recovered from organic phase by making contact three times with equal volumes of 1.0 M HNO₃.

3.4 Variation of diluents

Besides chloroform various diluents used in the present study are benzene, xylene, toluene, carbon tetra chloride, n-hexane, n-heptane cyclo hexane, nitrobenzene, dichloro methane which are of wide varieties in their chemical nature and dielectric constant. Maximum extraction efficiency was achieved with benzene as diluent (Table-2). Hence the same diluent was used in all these studies. Low % extraction was noticed from cyclohexane to nitrobenzene (82.3 to 69.5 %).

3.5 Analysis of iron in various samples

The precision and accuracy of the method of extraction for recovery of iron has been tested by analyzing food and pharmaceutical samples. Ten tablets were weighed accurately and finely powdered in a mortar. An amount of the powder equivalent to one tablet was transferred quantitatively to 100-ml volumetric flask and then 60 ml of 0.01 M H₂SO₄ was added. The mixture was shaken well for about 15 min. Then the mixture was diluted by 0.01 M H₂SO₄ solution to the mark and then filtered by Whatman filter paper No. 40. The first portion of filtrate was discarded. The clear solution obtained was used as a stock sample solution and different aliquots of prepared solutions were diluted with 0.01 M H₂SO₄ to produce different concentrations. 10.0 ml portions of the solution was extracted with 0.025 M TPAsO solutions as per the procedure described earlier. The results are presented in Table-3.

Table 1. Variation of acidity with %extraction

Acid Molarity (M)	HCl	H ₂ SO ₄	HNO ₃
0.5	69.82	74.82	72.23
1.0	75.52	78.54	78.54
1.5	83.92	83.92	81.92
2.0	86.29	88.26	83.20
2.5	88.68	88.76	83.93
3.0	89.75	90.23	85.83
4.0	90.36	92.48	79.36
4.5	92.13	94.53	78.75
5.0	92.50	96.55	75.83
6.0	96.52	97.87	65.89
7.0	96.87	97.91	62.54
8.0	98.45	98.18	59.65
9.0	99.45	99.22	59.65

Table 2. Effect of Diluents on Extraction

[Fe (III)] = 1.03×10^{-4} M; [H₂SO₄] = 9.0M; [TPAsO] = 2.5×10^{-2} M

Diluent	Dielectric constant	% extraction
Benzene	2.28	99.2
Chloroform	4.81	95.2
CCl ₄	2.23	95.8
Cyclo hexane	2.0	82.3
n-hexane	1.89	76.9
Dichloro methane	8.08	74.1
n-heptane	1.92	81.0
Toluene	2.43	78.8
Nitrobenzene	34.82	69.5

Table 3. Estimation of iron in food and pharmaceutical samples

Sample	Iron Present (%)	Iron found % by extraction recovery	
Ragi	3.00 ppm	2.88 ppm	96.00
Green gram	4.05 ppm	3.92 ppm	96.79
Ferrous fumerate (300mg)	114.10	113.48	99.53
Ferrous dextrin (50mg)	100.22	99.85	99.64

4. Conclusions

The proposed method is very simple, rapid and selective. It requires less than 20 min. time to extract and estimate iron content in natural food as well as pharmaceutical samples.

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